

Research Article

Association Between Somatic Symptoms and Depression - Anxiety - Stress Levels & Coping Strategies of Menopausal Women in Vijayawada City

Dr. P. SRINIVAS

Principal, TSR & ERR Government, Degree College, Pamarru

Corresponding Author: P. SRINIVAS

Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between Somatic Symptoms and depression, anxiety, stress levels in menopausal women. Investigating the Prevalence of Somatic Symptoms by Wing Menopause Rating scale. Investigating the prevalence of depression, stress and anxiety levels in menopausal women and discussing about Coping strategies for menopausal women. The results revealed 6% of menopausal women Severe level of depression, 91. have severe level of anxiety, 4% have Severe level of stress. The Correlation between Somatic Symptoms and depression, anxiety, stress highly Positive.

Keywords: Menopause, Somatic Symptoms, Psychological Symptoms, urogenital Symptoms, depression, anxiety, stream

Introduction

When a Women Permanently stops having menstrual Periods, She has reached the stage of life Called menopause. Menopause is said to be Complete when menstrual Periods have Ceased for One Continues year. Menopause is natural biological experience, which is an inevitable event in the lives of all women.

Genetics of menopause :

Twin and family studies have provided evidence that genetic factor's Contribute to the determination etal 1997, of menopause (Cramer etal. 1995; Togerson and Snieder etal. 1998) Krauss et al (1987) reported ovarian failure and premature menopause age of 24-37 years due to an interstitial deletion of the long -arm of the X Chromosome The estragon receptor a (ER-a) gene may be one of the Potential Candidate green underlying the Menopause.

Stages of MENOPAUSE:

Pre- Menopause :

Physical signs of menopause be give many years before your last menstrual period. Pre-menopause menopause refers to a women's reproductive ou fertile life, from the first menstrual period to the last.

Per menopause:

Per menopause refers to the years immediately before burring this time, your over gives gradually stop releasing ego and producing estrogens and other hormones (progesterone, androgen, testosterone)

Post-Menopause :

Post-menopause begins after your final menstrual Period and lasts for the rest of your life

Fast Facts on me pause :

- ❖ Menopause marks the end of a woman's fertility
- ❖ Symptoms of menopause include light sweats, hot flashes, mood fluctuations, and Cognitive changes.
- ❖ A reduction in estrogens levels can lead to the Symptoms of menopause
- ❖ There are a number of medical treatments and home remedies that can help with Symptoms including Hormone Replacement Therapy (HRT) And Self-management techniques.

Sign and Symptoms:

while menopause is not a disease or disorder, it does trigger some profound changes in a woman's body.

Irregular periods:

Changes to the to the menstrual pattern are the first he noticeable Symptoms of menopause Some May experience a period every 2 to 3 Weeks.. Other will not menstruate for months at a time.

Lower fertility:

Perimenopause is the 3 to 5 years Period before menopause. During the perimenopausal stage a woman's estrogens levels will drop significantly this reduces her Changes of becoming Pregnant.

Vaginal dryness:

Dryness, itching and discomfort of the Vagina tend occur during perimenopause. As a result Some women may experience dyspareunia or pain during sex

Hot flash :

A hot flash is a Sudden Sensation of heat in the upper body. It may Start in the face, neck or chest, and programs up word or downward.

Objectives of the study:

1. to Understand the prevalence of Somatic Symptoms menopausal women.
2. To Understand Depression, anxiety, stress levels among menopausal women.
3. to See the relation between Somatic Symptoms and depression, anxiety, stress levels in menopausal women
4. Coping strategies for menopausal women.

Hypothesis of the study:

1. Menopausal women may experience Severe Somatic Symptom
2. Menopausal women may experience Severe depression, anxiety, stress levels,
3. There is a relation between Somatic Symptom and depression, anxiety, stress levels among menopausal women.

Review of the literature:

Menopause is a part of every Stage women's life. It is the stage when the menstrual period permanently stop. The duration, Severity, and impact of menopausal Symptom vary from person to person, and Population to population. Jaszmann, van Lith and Zaat (1969) studied and were reported aches in Joints, bones and muscles that observed in 30% of women who were menstruating normally. There was a rise to a maximum of about 46% through 91 the menopause, with a subsequent decline to 37% at five to ten years after the menopause. Wood (1979) in a Comprehensive survey in Australia of all ages found no increase with Psychological Symptom investigated and indeed found a decline with age in headaches and irritability. Avis et al (2001) in a longitudinal study, found that associated with Symptoms such as hot flushes, Night Sweats and difficulty sleeping. Positively associated depression was positively but not with menopausal status or estradiol levels.

Universe of the study and sampling :

The Universe of the study was menopausal women of Vijayawada City. The study was conducted on a representative sample of 60 menopausal women through Random Sampling Method (Purposively) purposive sampling is also known as Judgmental, selection, subject Sampling.

Research tools used:

The success of any research endeavor is largely dependent upon the tools. The data Collection which are used for the present study following tools were used for data Collection

- . Menopause Rating Scale (MRS)
- . Depressive, Anxiety, stress scale (DASS)

Menopause Rating Scale:

Consist 11 items divided into 3 Subscale.

1. Somato-vegetative (heart discomfort, sleep problems/
2. psychological (depressed mood, anxiety, tiredness)
3. Urogenital (Sexual problems, bladder problem)

S.No	Domains	Items in the Scale
	Somatic	1,2,3,11
	Psychological	4,5,6,7
	Urogenital	8,9,10

Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale (DASS)

DASS-21 is a brief 21 item version of the full DASS, which originally consisted of 42 items.

Scores for the DASS-21 Sub-scales of depression, anxiety, and stress were derived by totaling the scores for each Sub-Scale and multiply by two-

S.No	Domains	Items in the Scale
	Depression	3,6,10,13,16,17,21
	Anxiety	2,4,7,9,15,19,20
	Stress	1,6,8,11,12,14,18

Data Collection procedure :

The Sample for the study was drawn from Vijayawada. The respondents were met individually and were appraised the purpose of the study

Results at Discussion:

The result they been clarified in to
 Section – I Descriptive Analys'
 Section – II Correlation Analysis

Objective:

To understand the prevalence of Somatic Supptury in Mempausy women.

Hypothes:

Monopausal women may experience Severe Somatic Syupta

Menopausal Women (N = 60)

Somatic Symptoms Severity	Frequency	Percentage
Nine	33	55
Mild	0	0
Moderate	16	26.66
Severe to V.Severe	11	18.33

above table reveals the 33 (55%) of Menopausal women have no Somatic Symptom. 16 (22.66%) of Menopausal some Show Moderate Somatic Symptom. 11 (18.337) of Menopausal women Showing Severe to extremely severe Somatic Symptom.

Objective:

to understand Depression, anxiety, Strem, liver any menopausal women.

Hypothesm:

Menopausal women (N-60)						
Severity	Depression		Anxiety		Stream	
Normal	F	P	F	P	F	P
	40	66.66	40	66.66	49	81.66
Mild	06	10	2	3.33	1	1.66
Moderate	08	13.33	9	15	6	10
Severe to V.Severe	06	10	9	15	4	6.66

Correlation analysis:

Correlation analysis is a statistical technique which measures the relationship of one variable to another

The pearson Correlation Coefficat, r, measury the Co-variation or arcciation between Variable

Objective :

To see the relation between Somatic Symtoms as depression, anxiety stream level in menopausal women.

Hypothesis :

There is a relation between Somatic Symtoms and anxiety stream level among menopausal women.

Coefficient of Correlation R Values			
Symptoms	Depression	Anxiety	Stream
Somatic	0.8135	0.8059	0.7869

Signature at 0.01 level-

It is evident that highly positive and Signifying relationship DASS and depression is little bit more than anxiety and stream. It is shown that as increase in DASS ($r=0.81$; $P<.01$) Somatic Symptoms and Depression Correlation value is 0.81, they are positively correlated with each other

There is a Signification relationship. Menopausal women who have Somatic Symptoms are Suffering with Depression Somatic Symptom and Anxiety Correlation value is 0.8059, they are also positively Correlated with each other. Somatic Symptom and stream Correlations Value is 0.7869 are also positively Correlated with Each Other.

Therefore hypothec No:3. Stating "That There is Signification Veluationship between Somatic Symptom ay depression, anxiety, Stream level among menopausal women" is alepted.

Discussion of Results:

Somatic Symptom and depression positively Correlated with each other (Correlation Value is 0.81)

Somatic Symptom and Anixety positively Correlated with each other (Correlation Value is 0.8059)

Somatic Symptom and Anixety positively Correlated with each other (Correlation Value is 0.7869)

Coping strategies:

1. Eat a healthy, balanced diet it can help your energy levels can mood.
2. Consider including two tablespoons of linseed oil in your diet
3. Undertake regular physical activity including aerobic, flexibility ay resistance activity
4. Quit Smooking women who Smoke may enter earlier than women Who don't Smoke.

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